

Ion implantation as a surface modification technique to improve localised corrosion of different stainless steels

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Abstract

The effect of silicon and argon implantation on the corrosion behaviour of different stainless steels (AISI 304, AISI 316L, AISI 317L and AISI 430) is discussed in this work. Silicon was implanted in order to generate an Si-rich region near the surface. Argon, as an inert gas, is supposed to have no chemical effects on the material. Different implantation doses (1×10^{14} , 5×10^{14} , 1×10^{15} ions/cm²) at an energy of 80 keV have been tested to optimise the implantation dose for each steel. Theoretical simulations using TRIM 96 computer code have been performed in order to estimate the depth profiles and to optimise the implantation parameters. The corrosion measurements were carried out in NaCl solution by using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). The surfaces have been characterised by SEM and AES. The experimental results showed that the effect of Si and Ar implantation mainly depends on the microstructure and/or composition of the stainless steels. Less compact structures and/or less amount of alloying elements (as occurs with the body centred cubic, ferritic AISI 430) achieve bigger changes with this modification, whereas on stainless steels with a larger amount of alloying elements and/or more compact structures (like the face centred cubic, austenitic AISI 317L) ion implantation slightly modifies the corrosion behaviour.

Keywords: Silicon and argon implantation; Corrosion behaviour; Stainless steels

1. Introduction

It is well known that the austenitic and ferritic stainless steels suffer different forms of localised corrosion [1], which is very dangerous leading to degradation/failure of structural stainless steels in service [2]. The damage is mostly due to halide ions, particularly chloride ions [1,3–5].

Corrosion is mostly a surface phenomenon, so the corrosion resistance is closely related to the composition and structure of surface films on metals [6]. Therefore, surface modification techniques are suitable to improve corrosion properties of a material [1].

The result of ion implantation into materials is the formation of a near-surface alloy of graded composition that has no well defined interface with respect to the substrate, in contrast to a deposition layer [7]. A graded alloy can be produced from the surface to the unchanged underlying

bulk alloy so that both the surface and the bulk can be independently optimised.

The addition of Si into stainless steels is known to enhance the corrosion resistance of the localised corrosion [2]. In this work, Si ion implantation was performed on four stainless steels (AISI 430, AISI 304, AISI 316L and AISI 317L) in order to evaluate the influence of the microstructure and/or steel composition on the improvement of the localised corrosion resistance.

The role of molybdenum in the corrosion resistance of stainless steels in chloride media is not yet clearly established [8]. Nevertheless, all previous studies have shown that Mo has a positive effect on pitting corrosion, even though it does not change the composition of the passive film [9].

Argon implantation was carried out on AISI 430 and AISI 304 stainless steels in order to confirm whether the improvement of the corrosion resistance was due to chemical effects produced by the silicon implanted or due to physical effects produced by ion implantation.

2. Experimental method

Four different commercial stainless steels (AISI 304, AISI 316L, AISI 317L and AISI 430), whose chemical compositions are given in Table 1, were used in this work. First, all 4X4-cm plate specimens were ground to a surface finish of SiC # 600 emery paper and implanted with different doses of Si (1×10^{14} , 5×10^{14} , 1×10^{15} ions/cm²) at an energy of 80 keV. All of these steels were implanted with Si. Additionally, the same experimental conditions were used on AISI 304 and AISI 430 implanted with Ar. Theoretical calculations have been made using the simulation program TRIM96 to provide an approach of the depth profile. Implanted specimens of 1X1 cm were characterised by Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) in a JEOL JAMP-50 mA with a 10-mA spot diameter.

The electrochemical tests were carried out in two different solutions. AISI 304 and AISI 430 were tested in a 0.5 M NaCl solution, whereas AISI 316L and AISI 317L were tested in a saturated NaCl solution due to their higher resistance to localised corrosion. The EIS experiments lasted 5 weeks and they were carried out at open circuit potential with an amplitude of 5 mV in the frequency range 10 mHz to 30 kHz. All experiments were recorded with a frequency response analyser Solar-tron 1255 and a potentiostat EG&G 283. The impedance spectra were analysed with the simulation Boukamp equivalent circuit software. After the electrochemical tests, samples were cleaned with distilled water, dried and examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersion spectroscopy (EDS).

3. Results and discussion

Table 2 shows the results of the projected range (PR), straggle (DPR) and the maximum implantation depth due to Si and Ar implantation at an energy of 80 keV, obtained by TRIM96 computational code.

For Si implantation, in all the stainless steels tested, RP, DRP as well as the maximum implantation depth have similar values due to the limitations of this program because it only take into account the

main alloying elements, but not the microstructure of the substrate.

For Ar implantation, lower values of these parameters were obtained, which means that Ar remains close to the surface, in a thinner region in comparison to Si implantation [10]. The bigger ion mass of Ar^d generates a higher damaged region and, according to the literature, an amorphous layer can be achieved [11] due to Ar- implantation.

AES spectra of the outer and inner sublayers on AISI 304 and AISI 430 stainless steels are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. A comparison between a non-implanted sample and a Si-implanted sample (1×10^{15} Si⁺/cm²) reveals a maximum contribution of the silicon in the outermost zone. In these layers (0 and 5 min of sputtering), silicon in the passive layer is oxidised as is shown by the displacement to lower energies of the Si_{L_{VV}} transition (92 eV). As the Fe concentration increases (15 and 20 min of sputtering), it is difficult to discriminate the amount of silicon present in the inner sublayers, because the main peak overlap with the Fe_{M_{VV}} transition (86 eV). After 30 min of sputtering the bulk metal is reached, as shown by the decrease of the oxygen peak and the increase of the Fe and Cr peaks.

Fig. 3 shows the Bode diagrams of all the Si- implanted samples after 1 h of immersion.

Si implantation has an important effect on AISI 304 (Fig. 3a) steel, in a way that this effect increases as the implantation dose increase. The higher implantation dose (1×10^{15} Si⁺/cm²) completely modifies the corrosion mechanism of this material with the apparition of a second time constant clearly defined. However, lower implantation doses means fewer modifications of the corrosion mechanism, although the intermediate implan- tation dose is enough to achieve lower corrosion rates than the non-implanted sample. In contrast, for the lower implantation dose (1×10^{14} Si⁺/cm²), implantation seems to be harmful, as can be observed in the low

frequency range. This negative effect of Si implantation for this sample could be due to the slight chemical effect of the implanted Si, which is not enough to hide the physical damage produced during the implantation process. Fitting of the impedance data with the Boukamp simulation program proposes two different models: a Randles circuit for the non-implanted sample and the one implanted with 1×10^{14} Si⁺/cm² and a double layer circuit for the most implanted samples (Fig. 3a).

The effect of Si implantation on AISI 316L is lower than on AISI 304 as is shown in the Bode diagram (Fig. 3b). The lower phase values in the low frequency range of the non-implanted sample revealed a higher corrosion rate. The higher implanted samples (1×10^{15} Si⁺/cm² and 5×10^{14} Si⁺ /cm²) showed a similar behavior whereas the lower implanted sample (1×10^{14} Si⁺/cm²) seems to have better behaviour, displaying bigger phase values than the other implanted samples. All the sam- ples, including the non-implanted one, showed a two time-constant mechanism and fit into a double layer circuit (Fig. 3b). Even though all implantation doses modify the corrosion rate, this change is not enough to produce a change of the corrosion mechanism. In 316L stainless steel, lower phase values are shown in the low–intermediate frequency range by all the implanted samples. This can be interpreted as evidence of the physical damage produced during the implantation process. The chemical effect of the implanted silicon on AISI 316L is lower than on AISI 304, as a consequence

of the extremely resistant passive layer. Even if $1 \times 10^{14} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$ is the lowest implantation dose, the radiation damage is also smaller, modifying in less quantity the passive layer.

Si implantation does not have a remarkable effect on the corrosion behaviour of AISI 317L stainless steel (Fig. 3c). Only the higher implantation dose ($1 \times 10^{15} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$) presents slight differences in comparison to the other ones. All samples fit into a double layer circuit in such a way that Si implantation does not modify the corrosion mechanism of this material. As occurs in AISI 316L stainless steel, higher radiation damage produced during the implantation process leads lower phase values of the most implanted sample and, therefore, a higher corrosion rate. AISI 317L stainless steel has an even more protective passive layer (higher Mo content) and a larger amount of alloying elements, which make it highly resistant.

The biggest differences on the corrosion mechanism are observed in AISI 430 (Fig. 3d). The effect of Si implantation is so important that all implantation doses completely modify the corrosion mechanism. Higher implantation doses mean bigger changes in corrosion behaviour. Thus, the most implanted sample ($1 \times 10^{15} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$) completely changes the spectra showing a three time-constant mechanism. Some authors suggested the formation of an amorphous layer in the outermost zone [12], but for higher implantation doses than the ones used in our work. Although this cannot be confirmed by us, it could explain the improvement of the corrosion rate. A triple layer circuit fit with spectra, whereas lower implantation doses fit into a double layer circuit. By contrast, for the non-implanted sample a monolayer circuit is fitted, as occurred on AISI 304.

Changes in the electrochemical response for both Si-implanted AISI 304 and AISI 430 stainless steels can be due to a silicon oxide sublayer in the outermost region of the passive layer, which improve the corrosion resistance [13]. This silica-like sublayer has been already detected by AES (Figs. 1 and 2).

Fig. 4 shows the Bode diagrams for all Si-implanted stainless steels after 5 weeks of immersion.

For longer immersion periods on AISI 304 (Fig. 4a), the $1 \times 10^{14} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$ implanted sample improved the corrosion behaviour. Now, all the implanted samples have slightly lower corrosion rates than the non-implanted one. In general, physical damage is more obvious during the first stages of the experiments. The two time-constants mechanism of the most implanted sample ($1 \times 10^{15} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$) seem to vanish, although at 5 weeks continue showing the most differentiated spectra. Two different behaviours can be seen: on one side, the non-implanted sample and the $1 \times 10^{14} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$ implanted sample. On the other side, doses higher than $5 \times 10^{14} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$ continue to show a different corrosion mechanism.

SEM examinations of the most implanted sample revealed a surface in good condition (Fig. 5) with some dark and isolated products, mainly composed of silicon, shown in previous work [13]. After 5 weeks of immersion, a Bode diagram of AISI 316L is shown in Fig. 4b. All the implanted samples showed improved behaviour, showing higher phase values in the intermediate-low frequency range. This improvement is more evident for doses higher than $5 \times 10^{14} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$. All samples still have

two time- constants, although the $1 \times 10^{14} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$ implanted sample was better defined than the other ones. This means that the lowest silicon dose is not able to achieve the same recovery as fast as ones with higher implantation doses.

There is a recovery on the corrosion resistance of the passive layer of AISI 317L, although this change is smaller than on AISI 316L, as revealed by the enhancement of the phase values in the intermediate frequency range. The improvement is more evident for doses higher than $5 \times 10^{14} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$. All samples still have two time constants, although the $1 \times 10^{14} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$ implanted sample was better defined than the other ones. This means that the lowest silicon dose is not able to achieve the same recovery as fast as ones with higher implantation doses.

There is a recovery on the corrosion resistance of the passive layer of AISI 317L, although this change is smaller than on AISI 316L, as revealed by the enhancement of the phase values in the intermediate frequency range. The improvement is more evident for doses higher than $5 \times 10^{14} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$, whose spectra show values of the phase above that of the non-implanted sample. SEM examination of the most implanted sample revealed a surface with hardly any defects (Fig. 6).

A Bode diagram of AISI 430 after 5 weeks is shown in Fig. 4d. Higher implantation results in lower corrosion rates. In this case, the effect of Si-implantation lasts longer than on the other stainless steels, so that all implanted samples maintain the same corrosion mechanism from the beginning, but with the most superficial layer damaged due to a partial dissolution in the electrolyte. By contrast, AISI 430 without implantation fits the pit circuit already mentioned.

SEM examinations of the non-implanted sample of AISI 430 revealed the presence of pits along the surface and as the implantation dose increased, less quantities of pits were observed. In this way, some superficial defects of small size were found on the sample implanted with the highest dose (Fig. 7).

Argon implantation has only been performed in AISI 304 and AISI 430 steels, where a larger improvement of the localised corrosion resistance was achieved with Si implantation.

Bode diagrams of Ar-implanted samples of AISI 304 after 1 h of immersion is shown in Fig. 8a. As occurs with Si implantation, EIS spectra are similar for all samples, except for the most implanted one, which shows two time-constants clearly defined. As the exposure time increase (Fig. 8b), a two time-constant mechanism began to appear in the other $1 \times 10^{14} \text{ Ar}^+/\text{cm}^2$ and $5 \times 10^{14} \text{ Ar}^+/\text{cm}^2$ implanted samples, but was not as well defined as the most implanted one. The corrosion rates of the implanted samples are slower than the non-implanted one, and the most implanted sample maintains the best behaviour for longer periods of time. A comparison between Si implantation (Fig. 4a) and Ar implantation after 5 weeks of immersion (Fig. 8a) reveals that the above-mentioned differences between the most implanted sample and the other samples, are bigger and last longer for Ar-implanted samples. The improvement in the localised corrosion for $1 \times 10^{15} \text{ Ar}^+/\text{cm}^2$ could be explained by the structural changes introduced by Ar implantation, which causes amorphisation of the

near surface layers [11]. This structural change was already detected by Jedrekowiak et al. [14] on AISI 304 steel at a dose of 1×10^{15} ions/cm². This superficial modification could promote the creation of a more protective passive film.

Implanted samples (1×10^{15} Ar⁺/cm² and 5×10^{14} Ar⁺ions/cm²) fit into a double layer circuit at low and high periods of immersion, whereas the less implanted sample (1×10^{14} Ar⁺/cm²) also fit into a double layer circuit for short periods but with the outer layer damaged for longer periods. In this case, this implantation dose is not enough to produce a continuous amorphous region but isolated zones. A Bode diagram of Ar-implanted AISI 430 stainless steel for 1 h of immersion (Fig. 9a) showed a change in the corrosion behaviour in comparison to the non-implanted sample. These differences are not as big as with Si implantation. Ar implantation seems to be harmful, as revealed by the lower phase values and corrosion rates higher than the non-implanted sample. For longer exposure periods (Fig. 9b), the most implanted sample behaves in a different way than the other implanted samples, close to the non-implanted one. The phase values are even lower than the ones shown for shorter immersion times, which indicates a worst behaviour as the time increase. All samples fit a pitting circuit. In conclusion, for AISI 430 stainless steel, Ar implantation has a harmful effect due to the big size of the Ar⁺ ion which causes significant physical damage when it is implanted on less compact structures, as confirmed by SEM with a larger amount of defects (Fig. 10).

As the number of alloying elements increases, the corrosion resistance is also increased and therefore, the beneficial effects of ion implantation are much more difficult to appreciate. It can be concluded that, for highly resistant stainless steels such as 316L and 317L, higher implantation doses must be applied to achieve a critical dose, which causes a change in the electrochemical behaviour. As the electrochemical effects of ion implantation are not appreciated, only physical effects can be seen, causing damage to the passive layer and therefore decreasing the protective properties of this layer. Bigger changes on the corrosion mechanisms were promoted by lower implantation doses on the ferritic AISI 430 stainless steel due to the less compact structure. This means that this kind of microstructure (BCC) is more sensible to ion implantation. Ar implantation on this stainless steel is supposed to have larger changes on the corrosion behaviour, but the microstructure is not capable of assuming the changes produced by the heavier Ar^d. A decrease in the localised corrosion resistance with increasing dose has been previously reported [11], which is due to the defects and inhomogeneities generated by ion implantation.

Moreover, argon implantation mainly leads to structural changes, but may also lead to chemical changes where Ar⁺ is only a tool to introduce these changes, so all modifications of the EIS spectra are supposed to be mainly due to the physical effects produced during the implantation process. The results obtained for Ar implanted AISI 304 could explain the changes proposed on the passive layer of AISI 316L and 317L Si- implanted, where a double layer mechanism were proposed.

The experimental results conclude that the effect of Ar implantation is greater than Si implantation. Si implantation produces a silicon enrichment capable of hiding the physical damage, even though the radiation damage is not as great as during Ar implantation. The surface modification introduced by

ion implantation strongly depends on the stainless steel used.

4. Conclusions

The surface modification produced by ion implantation depends on both the implanted ions and the target. In such a way, the ferritic structure is more sensible to ion implantation.

Silicon ion implantation is an effective technique to delay the pitting corrosion of AISI 304 and AISI 430 stainless steels in NaCl solution. On AISI 304, a dose of 1×10^{15} Si⁺/cm² completely modified the corrosion mechanism, although a 5×10^{14} Si⁺/cm² dose is enough to provide protection against pitting corrosion. For AISI 430, silicon implantation doses as low as 1×10^{14} Si⁺/cm² can completely change the corrosion mechanism.

On AISI 316L and AISI 317L, silicon implantation ranging from 1×10^{14} Si⁺/cm² to 1×10^{15} Si⁺/cm² slightly decreases the corrosion rate in aqueous chloride containing solutions and does not promote a modification of the corrosion mechanism. The effect of higher numbers of alloying elements (mainly Mo) hides the effect of silicon implantation.

Argon implantation on AISI 304 increases the localised corrosion resistance. Doses above 1×10^{15} Si⁺/cm² cm strongly modify the corrosion mechanism by producing an amorphous layer in the near surface which could favor a more protective passive layer. In contrast, argon implantation produces a harmful effect on AISI 430, decreasing pitting corrosion resistance.

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TABLES

Table 1

Chemical composition of AISI 304, AISI 430, AISI 316L and AISI 317L stainless steels (wt.%)

	Si	Mn	Ni	Cu	Cr	P	Mo	Co	C	S	N	V	Sn	Ti	Nb	B
AISI 304	0.44	1.52	8.19	0.29	18.30	0.031	0.21	0.12	0.065	0.002	0.038	–	0.013	–	–	–
AISI 316L	0.36	1.12	10.64	0.34	16.98	0.033	2.13	0.16	0.033	0.001	0.046	0.09	0.010	0.013	0.021	0.003
AISI 317L	0.35	1.57	12.96	0.25	18.42	0.028	3.10	0.09	0.023	0.003	0.055	0.08	0.003	0.008	0.009	0.003
AISI 430	0.32	0.3	0.21	0.03	16.53	0.020	0.01	0.02	0.064	0.001	0.032	–	–	–	–	–

Table 2

Projected range (PR), straggle (DPR) and maximum implantation depth of Si^a and Ar^a implanted samples of AISI 304, AISI 430, AISI 316L and AISI 317L stainless steels

Implanted element	Target	PR (nm)	DPR (nm)	Maximum depth (nm)
Si	AISI 304	5130	2340	f13600
	AISI 316L	5130	2340	f12600
	AISI 317L	5120	2340	f12600
	AISI 430	5190	2360	f13400
Ar	AISI 304	3830	1690	f10000
	AISI 430	3870	1720	f9000

FIGURES

Fig. 1. Auger spectra of the non-implanted and 1×10^{15} Si^+/cm^2 implanted AISI 304 stainless steel with different sputtering times. The line marks the position of Si.

Fig. 2. Auger spectra of the non-implanted and 1×10^{15} Si^+/cm^2 implanted AISI 430 stainless steel with different sputtering times. The line marks the position of Si.

a)

b)

c)

d)

Fig. 3. Bode diagrams of Si-implanted (a) AISI 304 stainless steel, (b) AISI 430 stainless steel, (c) AISI 316L stainless steel, and (d) AISI 317L stainless steel with different implantation doses after 1 h of immersion.

Fig. 4. Bode diagrams of Si-implanted (a) AISI 304 stainless steel, (b) AISI 430 stainless steel, (c) AISI 316L stainless steel, and (d) AISI 317L stainless steel with different implantation doses after 5 weeks of immersion.

Fig. 5. Micrograph of the $1 \times 10^{15} \text{ Si}^+/\text{cm}^2$ implanted AISI 304 stainless steel after 5 weeks of immersion

Fig. 6. Micrograph of the 1×10^{15} Si^+/cm^2 implanted AISI 317L stainless steel after 5 weeks of immersion.

Fig. 7. Micrograph of the 1×10^{15} Si^+/cm^2 implanted AISI 430 stainless steel after 5 weeks of immersion.

a)

b)

Fig. 8. Bode diagrams of Ar-implanted AISI 304 stainless steel with different implantation doses after (a) 1 h and (b) 5 weeks of immersion.

a)

b)

Fig. 9. Bode diagrams of Ar-implanted AISI 430 stainless steel with different implantation doses after (a) 1 h and (b) 5 weeks of immersion.

Fig. 10. Micrograph of the 1×10^{15} Ar^+/cm^2 implanted AISI 430 stainless steel after 5 weeks of immersion.